

Supplementary material for “Unpacking enablers and disablers of transformation: Insights from Central and Eastern Europe as white spots on the global knowledge map“

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1 Characteristics of research participants

Table 1. List of interviewed transformative actors with their general descriptions

ID	Form/Type of organization (network/initiative/...)	Nexus sector (energy/land-food)
1	Network	Energy
2	Association	Land-food
3	Initiative	Food
4	Association	Land-food
5	Association	Land-food
6	Initiative	Land-food
7	Network	Energy

2 Interview guide for in-depth semi-structured interviews

Greetings and introductions

1. What does your organisation/network do?
2. What is your organisation/network trying to achieve? / What are your organisation's/network's goals?
 - a. What is the broader need / problem that your organisation / network is aiming at?
 - b. What is the key motivation?
3. Are you part of any relevant national / regional network?
4. What do you personally do within your organisation/network?
5. What are you proud of/what have you achieved within your organization/network?
6. How did you achieve this particular success?
7. What were the specific steps that helped you achieve success?
8. What were the external conditions that helped you achieve these steps?
 - a. Were there any specific policies that you find helpful? Can you name them and explain how?
9. What other external conditions would have helped you [but did not happen]?
10. Who do you think are the key stakeholders that have helped you achieve this change?
 - a. Were there any specific institutions that you find helpful? Can you name them and explain their role?
11. From your today's perspective, are there other stakeholders whose support would have helped you achieve your success?
 - a. Would have a state involvement would help you in any way to achieve your success (e.g., ministries, new policy frameworks)?
12. What direction of action do you plan to take in the future?/What are your plans for the future?
13. In light of past experience, what would you do the same in the future?
 - a. Why?
14. In light of past experience, what would you do differently in the future?
 - a. Why?
15. Who else do you think has something to say on this topic?
16. Do you feel that something else should have been said but wasn't?
17. Would you like to participate in any further project activities?

3 Quotes from the in-depth semi-structured interviews supporting the resulting enablers and disablers of transformative change

The excerpts from the structured data used in the text are presented in the English translation of the original literal transcript in the Czech language to carry the experience of the research participants.

Table 2: List of enablers and disablers on the operational level with supporting quotes from the interviews

Enabler	Supporting quote
External support	<p>“And it is interesting that I have noticed something similar in another movement, which also created the first bioregion in the Czech Republic, where someone from the outside also had to come in, which is often criticized as a neocolonial motive, that someone comes to you, someone from a different environment, comes to tell you how things should be done or can be done, but in fact without these contributions and initiatives and some kind of motivated actors who have a general vision and are able and willing to motivate and cooperate with locals and help them define their needs and assist them. For example, raising funds for their activities, etc. So the motivation of the outside actor who comes in is actually important.” (R2)</p>
	<p>“I should probably also mention the tremendous, absolutely essential support from German biodynamic companies, which have actually been financing it from the beginning... Well, "supporting" is too weak a word... They are de facto financing it. In addition to grants, in addition to a number of... We have a Czech-German cooperation fund. And the key player is a German biodynamic company (...) which has contributed significantly to the establishment of the operation and also to the farm investments that we have taken over, which we have leased.” (R2)</p>
Sense of collectivity	<p>“Although I think that from the beginning we had, and in my opinion still have, a large community of people who support us in various ways, whether financially or materially, or by meeting here regularly because they want to support the project, that was definitely also important.” (R3)</p>
	<p>“Well, I think that the organic agriculture sector played a very important role, which is a somewhat unstructured group of institutions that pushed [organic agriculture] forward. NGOs or universities and like-minded people, such as the Czech University of Agriculture and its department, simply these people who were involved in organic farming there, they gave us the</p>

	feeling that it was worth it and that someone at the higher levels was interested in it, and they provided us with material support—like an auditorium and students for practical training when we needed to weed and things like that.” (R5)
Personal qualities	<p>“And that was one thing, that we stuck with it even though it seemed like complete nonsense and everyone told us it was complete nonsense, it was like—do things that people want, right, don't do something that nobody wants— so we did something that nobody wanted from the beginning, and we knew that it was needed by a higher entity, like the landscape, nature, it needs people to care for it, to be interested in it, to approach it as something that doesn't just produce potatoes, but also for consumers to develop this relationship there (...) Well, and the second level was that we then tested those models physically, that we didn't just talk about it and research it, but that we then actually established community farming and somehow experienced it ourselves, and we then built on that and developed it further. So I think that's quite an important aspect, that people often jump into it without really knowing what they're getting into and without having thought it through, but they have this idea that they somehow stick to. And to this day, these projects, even though I haven't been there for couple of years, are still running and running well, and the people there are happy and it brings them something.” (R5)</p> <p>“I always say that I'm a bit of a punk or pirate in my thinking—not in a political sense, but basically, if it's not written down, I'll create the rules myself somehow and start implementing them. Of course, my colleagues are more inclined to need things to be anchored in some way, so that helps.” (R7)</p>
Ability to act flexibly and adaptably	“When something doesn't work out, I learn from it immediately and then start doing things differently, so this question is difficult for me because when I feel that I should do something differently, I start doing it differently. It's not like we set something up and then follow through the next 10 years because we have a 10-year plan. No, (...) after each delivery (...) we evaluate it, we monitor it, and when we don't feel comfortable with it, something isn't working, we say to ourselves, this was really stupid. Or even with some form of communication or cooperation, so we stop and look for... hey, let's do it differently, so when something doesn't feel right, we immediately look for a way to change it.” (R6)
Disabler	Supporting quote
Embeddedness in outdated concepts	“And I think that organic farming and the principles and agricultural practices of organic farming have been stagnating for the last, let's say, 10-15 years, that organic farming, in principle, even though it is the only alternative, environmentally

	friendly form of farming that is legislatively recognized across Europe, tends to follow the path of exceptions.” (R2)
Unavailability of data on transformation	“Yes, research, another area that we simply cannot keep up with, we don't have rigorous research, we have soft data, but something rigorous. If, for example, the specific impacts of staying on farms were measured in Czechia... we don't have that. Such research exists in the Netherlands, it's in Dutch, and now I have read something from Sweden, some article. But it's not much, so it's harder to argue why politicians should support it, why healthcare or psychiatric care should be more interested in it.” (R4)
Scatteredness and heterogeneity of motivations	“So what is missing here is actually a link and the promotion of our own interests. That is one of the reasons why our organization does not have its own advocacy and lobbying strategy and platform. Among other things, it is because we did not know for a long time who we were speaking for, or rather, we knew who we were speaking for, but we did not know how many of us there were.” (R2)
Missing infrastructure	“One of the most frequently discussed topics related to community energy, (...) is the capacity of the distribution network, especially the low-voltage. Distributors are, of course, obliged to continuously invest in this infrastructure and develop it, (...) the interest in the construction of renewable energy sources, especially photovoltaics, and hopefully other sources in the future, is growing rapidly, and with that, of course, capacity is gradually filling up, and now we are running into the problem that there has been no investment in this infrastructure for the last 10 years, and as a result, distribution companies often mention the fact that there is nowhere to connect these sources and they will overload the distribution network.” (R1)

Table 3: List of enablers and disablers on the structural level with supporting quotes from the interviews

Enabler	Supporting quote
Policies and strategies	“And then in the social sphere, we have (...) the National Plan for the Inclusion of People with Disabilities, where we also have social farming as a tool for work integration, but then I think also leisure activities in the countryside, so those are the key ones. Then we also have the European Economic and Social Committee. It drafted a statement in 2012, specifically on social farming, and about three years ago, another statement was drafted where social farming is mentioned, but I think that relates more to the development of rural and suburban areas, so it's also integrated there as a concept, but it's not a specific policy. So these strategic plans or strategies are useful to refer to when you want to push something through; there are many of them, yes. We can also mention the Green Deal, and (...) the

	National Recovery Plan and many more, it probably depends on what each person finds.” (R4)
Transposing EU directives	“Yes, national and European policies are definitely an external factor. We actually started at a time when things were beginning to change in some way and green issues were starting to find their way into strategies and documents, and gradually even into financial resources.” (R5)
	“In the Czech Republic, relevant legislation is currently being prepared, because the concept of community energy is embedded in two European directives. They call it energy communities, and community energy is essentially an umbrella term. We were supposed to transpose one of these directives into Czech legislation by the end of 2020 and the other by mid-2021. Specifically, these are the directives on the promotion of renewable energy sources and the directive on the internal market for electricity. Each of them actually addresses energy communities from a different perspective and each defines one type of energy community. (...) However, subsidy programs are being prepared in parallel (...) energy communities and community energy are actually very new concepts in Czechia, and what happens is that, for example, the Ministry of the Environment or the State Environmental Fund may not know exactly how to actually approach this energy community actor and how to set up subsidy programs that are available through the Modernization fund, the National Recovery Plan, and other European funds, how to actually set the conditions so that it really serves its purpose and supports energy communities in their current form, and we helped to co-create several subsidy programs that more or less concern energy communities.” (R1)
ESG reporting obligation	“(…) They are well aware that they must become greener because financing is tied to it. Now there is the EU taxonomy, ESG criteria, which they will have to meet and report on. Community energy and electricity sharing are among the tools they can use to help themselves in this regard, thereby improving their ESG reporting and securing more attractive financing for their projects. (...)” (R1)
Subsidies and grants	“Well, I think that the common agricultural policy of the previous programme period (...). The one that started to finance organic farming in the long term as a universal mechanism was in 2009, so that was a big turning point; it became a financial mechanism that says, Look, farmer, if you meet these above-standard requirements, you'll get a lot of extra money. (...) I think it was a huge turning point for the system.” (R5)
	“Yes, the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of the Environment gave us a lot of money for various projects from these subsidy programs for non-profit organizations, so in my opinion, they legitimized what we do, that it's OK for them.” (R5)
	“At the same time, however, a new subsidy program will be launched to support the establishment of energy communities under the national environmental program, with CZK 99,000,000 allocated to support 40 energy community projects. We were involved in the creation of this program, which supports soft measures such as technical feasibility studies, legal analyses, drafting of sharing

	agreements, economic analysis of the return on investment and the operation of energy communities, which are actually the steps that you, as an aspiring energy community, have to take, but until now no subsidy program has reimbursed you for them. There has always been only investment support (...), but now we are at a stage where we have managed to create a program that will support all these soft measures, and we will definitely promote it based on this.” (R1)
Digitalisation of various administrative processes	“It's great that a lot of things work (...) like basic digitization, such as data inbox, so that people don't have to go to the city hall, that's kind of nice.” (R3)
Digitalisation of data management	“In practice, this means that by mid-2026, there will be a transitional EDC [“Energy Data Center”; <i>note: a company that collects and shares data on community energy</i>] that will provide some basic data sharing and community energy, but from mid-2026, the EDC should be fully operational and should actually help not only with data sharing from community energy, but it will also help to put into practice concepts such as accumulation, aggregation, flexibility, and the provision of support services, which is great because it will greatly help with digitalisation and decentralisation, because then we will be able to realistically imagine that energy communities will be able to use the provision of flexibility services and, if they have accumulation, it will really help to support decentralisation.” (R1)
Disabler	Supporting quote
Excessive bureaucracy	“And in the end, these obligations usually make sense, such as those concerning occupational safety and hygiene, etc. I'm not saying they should be cancelled, but it's very difficult to understand them (...), the rules are set up in such a way that we simply don't understand them, so we have to pay someone else to do it for us. So it's a huge extra cost, a lot of administration, a lot of conditions to make everything work properly, and every three months something comes up that we're supposed to comply with, (...) and that's still happening to us even after five years.” (R3)
	“But generally, I feel that there are so many things we have to comply with, and if we don't, we face huge fines. Above all, you either have to have a lot of money and pay for good lawyers and accountants to take care of everything, or at least explain everything in detail and check everything. Or you have to study it yourself, but that means either doing it for 20 years and doing it badly and then learning it after those 20 years, or studying at least four bachelor's degrees in a row from these different fields.” (R3)
	“If it were possible to simplify the paperwork involved in these applications, or to reduce the [paperwork in the] rural development program, not waiting for the law, but creating something administratively simpler for those farmers who may have smaller acreage. Or they have a social impact that can be measured in some other way than by the number of people they employ, that there will also be some softer forms that can be measured and simply described, because the paperwork is actually very demanding. The same applies to control mechanisms, because a farmer who produces something must meet all the same standards as any other producer,

	<p>as if he wanted to sell his production anywhere else in the world. I don't think that a small farmer who has 5 or 10 hectares and has his own customer base, which actually controls the quality, would still need to meet the same quality requirements as if he wanted to export to the United States, for example.” (R4)</p>
Lack of supportive legislation	<p>“Yes, I think that's the point I'm trying to make—that bottom-up activities exist, but there is still no connection to actors who can systematically scale these alternatives through regulations, legislation, etc. It still doesn't come together.” (R2)</p>
	<p>“When I was looking for the legal entity myself, there was sufficient diversity for non-profit organizations (...). Whereas if I want to become a for-profit company in the Czech Republic, it can only be an s.r.o. [limited liability company/private limited company] or an a.s. [joint-stock company]. And that's just not enough, and at that point, it doesn't distinguish us from those who are just in it for the money, because when I'm an s.r.o., my mission is to generate profit. Period. (...) And everything else is basically my hobbies, which I don't have to do at all (...), it's basically up to my good will that I and the people I bring in will create it, but it's really still a voluntary activity (...) that basically, if you want to do business, it's not just about the money, that every business has an impact on the society we live in, on the environment.” (R6)</p>
	<p>“For me, in general, it's more of a question, or rather, I see social enterprises as a kind of band-aid for the fact that the system is broken. In the short term, I think it's great to try to improve conditions for social enterprises so there are fewer obstacles in our way. But in the long term, I would like to see the legislation changed in such a way that we are less and less needed and that it is done in a centralized, organized way, cooperating with non-profit organizations to some extent, etc.” (R3)</p>
Distortion of transformative topics in legislation	<p>“One official initiated it, and we are part of it, and it is interesting that this is a case where the state administration recognized an alternative as existing and relevant and decided to systematically embrace and support it. Paradoxically, we perceive this as a major threat. Because we feel that we are actually losing control over the content. And that the effort to systematically embrace it and perhaps eventually create some kind of subsidy program, to embrace it legislatively, we actually perceive (...) that the concept and the content of the concept are being flattened.” (R2)</p>
Top-down oriented legislative/policy making	<p>“When we talk about food systems, the common denominator is still the CAP [Common Agricultural Policy] (...) I think that the common characteristic is that it follows individual regulations, that the discussion is actually very technical. This ensures that it meets the needs of officials, politicians, legislators, and actors responsible for formulating the common agricultural policy. And so far, it has not been conducted at a general conceptual level, such as what impact the food system has on healthcare or public health. So far, it has focused a lot on the health of nature, or rather on policies and efforts to prevent soil and ecosystem degradation, etc., but I still don't see any links to the health of society, the precarious work of agricultural (...) or decent working conditions for farmers.” (R2)</p>

	<p>“There is strong pressure from the top-down approach, which is based on classic policy-making scenarios involving expert knowledge and experts. However, this model for national policy-making has long been disproved: without the involvement of the public and other active stakeholders, such policies and regulations are meaningless, or their impact is highly problematic.” (R2)</p>
Sectoralism	<p>“That's why we're generally difficult for our partners to grasp, because educating farmers is something the Ministry of Education doesn't understand, and caring for the landscape is something the Ministry of Agriculture doesn't understand, and so on. So it's actually a disadvantage to try to be this connector, because these institutions have silo thinking.” (R5)</p>
The rigidity of the Czech governance system	<p>“We do not rely on one specific model, unlike the state administration; the Ministry of Agriculture, which tends to always choose a certain track, typically digitalization or robotization of agriculture, as major, overarching themes through which they push everything, which are supposed to solve everything. We believe that it is important to support a wide range of different approaches, but this is also extremely difficult for the state administration to grasp, both in terms of recognition and possible support, and I think that the role of the state administration is still unclear. The position of the state administration towards alternatives is unclear, and the alternatives do not have a clear position and expectations from the state administration.” (R2)</p>
Subsidies	<p>“Well, even though we talked about those policies so much, and also about those prices, it's still actually disadvantaged. I don't know how it is in other areas, but the food industry in particular is very complex in terms of pricing, precisely because large corporations and companies often have significant advantages, either in terms of taxes or subsidies, which means they have external resources that are not reflected in the price, and so they can afford to have a much lower price, plus they also use practices where they work with the end price and try to reduce the price for the grower so that they have a large margin for their own profit. For us as entrepreneurs in this sector, where we try to set prices in the opposite way and leave the price for the grower, we are left with very little room to maneuver so that our prices are not completely astronomical, and we really have to think very carefully about our costs and our needs.” (R6)</p>
	<p>“We were actually discouraged by how the subsidies work, so we didn't even apply for them. Today, we had a cooperative meeting here, where we discussed whether to submit the application we have already started working on with another organization, a social enterprise that provides catering services. It looks like we won't submit it because it's so demanding and complicated and, to some extent, risky that we'd rather give up on it.” (R3)</p>
Tax system	<p>“Well, it would certainly be easier if the conditions were better, or if everyone had the same conditions in theory, but in practice, when you're a large company, you get various tax breaks and so on, which we as a small business don't have, so very often the tax burden is also high, or actually, what would help start-ups is that the taxation of labor for employees is really high. So, basically, finding a way to support</p>

	<p>small local entrepreneurs. At least in the beginning, because going from volunteering to having full-time employees...” (R6)</p>
	<p>“If I were to relate this to us, then I think I speak for both us as small business owners and as employees when I say that the tax system simply has to change, in terms of income tax. It needs to ease the burden on the small [businesses] and increase it on the large [businesses], because the tax burden on both sides is terribly high. And economically, of course, it makes no sense at all, because the more money a person has, the more they save and the less they put back into the economy, so we need people who are low-income to have more money left so they can spend more. This applies equally to our employees, who would have more of their wages left, and it applies to the restaurant industry, because those people will have more money to spend.” (R3)</p>
Purchasing power	<p>“On the contrary, we need people with low incomes to have more money left to spend. This applies equally to our employees, who would have more of their wages left after tax, and to the restaurant industry, because these people will have more money to spend. To put it bluntly, a rich person will not go to a restaurant more than three times a day, but a poor person who goes there once a week or not at all will start going to that restaurant, so we simply need these people to have more money to spend in the economy, which will give us higher revenues and allow us to pay these people more.” (R3)</p>
	<p>“Among other things, this would probably mean a radical increase in food prices so that farmers could receive a decent wage, but this would also mean that either the whole society would have to receive an unconditional basic income, or wages would have to be increased, which would mean a new transformation of the economy.” (R2)</p>
Missing political personas supportive of transformation	<p>„Well, if you mean an external condition, such as a specific politician who would take up the issue as their own, then that would probably be useful for us. We tried a little through one member of the European Parliament, and we even went to Brussels to see her, but she didn't really take up the issue as her own. She is from a political party where the social aspect is not that important to them. Yes, so it would definitely be good if another political party, or even this one, started to see it as something that even though may not generate immediate financial returns, doesn't generate profit, but in the long term, when more people in general, not just in rural areas, have jobs, or don't rely on the gray economy, or get the support they deserve, the country as a whole will simply prosper more. So definitely concrete political support.“ (R4)</p>
	<p>“It would be good if the Ministry of Agriculture appointed someone to take responsibility for this issue, because there is a commission there, which is informal, an association, a non-profit organization, but then whenever we need something, we have to go through someone else, but no one there is pushing the issue individually, or has responsibility for it. We usually go through people from the Rural Development Program or through the National Rural Network. But we don't want a union; we just want someone who understands it and who would also be a representative for other ministries or other institutions, even at the international negotiating level.” (R4)</p>

Lack of multi-actor platforms representing the interests of diverse groups	“We feel that we don't have much power in the system, that we don't have any kind of power that we could exercise (...). That we are actually irrelevant to... We clearly have relevant expert knowledge that is being used, but that we could speak for a specific social group—that's complicated, and I hope that will come in time, because in the Czech Republic, we don't even have any platform representing consumers.” (R2)
Municipalities as important yet inactive	„Well, from my point of view, it's classic leakage. This issue hasn't leaked through yet. (...) the priorities are elsewhere. And also, especially at the municipal level, a lot depends on specific people and their backgrounds and their interests and their desires and so on. So when you have a mayor who has an agricultural background and is also aware of the environmental problems we have here, then it's easier to deal with them. And again, it's about raising awareness of these issues in society in general, so the percentage of mayors who understand this is increasing simply because awareness in society is higher.“ (R5)
Increasing bureaucratic requirements	<p>“But for distribution companies, to come back to that, it is of course extra work, because they have to prepare it, it takes two years, but on the other hand, they get money for it, 0.8 billion from the National Recovery Plan. Nevertheless, that money has to be used up by a certain date, so that should be an incentive for them to do it, but it is a burden on their capacity. That's actually the issue with distribution companies: why they are, quote unquote, against it. And (...) in the end, it will be able to help them or be useful to them, but it creates extra work for them, not only in terms of the EDC [<i>“Energy Data Center”</i>; <i>note: a company that collects and shares data on community energy</i>], but also in terms of increasing the capacity of the distribution network and additional investments. At the same time, they will be the ones who will actually ensure the sharing in practice. So naturally, when a change like this happens, which I dare say is really big in the energy sector, it is clear that they are resisting.” (R1)</p> <p>“Personally, I wish social workers or the field of social work were more progressive. We deal with a lot of issues; it's very fragmented, and these, let's say, innovations are very difficult to implement. But it's a double-edged sword, the agricultural world is too far removed from solving specific problems, such as drug addiction, foster care, or debt issues, so when you say oh, social farming, but how will it solve homelessness, it could partially solve or help, but these social problems are so complex that any novelty or idea is a burden or a hindrance or an additional area...” (R4)</p>
Power imbalances between small and large actors	“(...) we are a special country where agriculture is controlled by a few large entrepreneurs, large agribusinesses that influence how European agricultural policy is formed and implemented in our legislation, and the voice of small farmers is still too small, so the rules are set up in such a way that only the big players can benefit from them, and the small ones are often not even big enough to get even a small subsidy, so it really makes a big difference whether I produce cheese in a large dairy farm or I am a small [producer].” (R6)
	“The Ministry of the Environment was generally more inclined towards transposition and the introduction of the concept of community

Private influence over the governance system	energy into practice than, for example, the Ministry of Industry and Trade, but not because the Ministry of Industry and Trade resisted itself. Rather, the Ministry of Industry and Trade faces great lobbying pressure from all sides in the field of energy, much, much greater than, for example, the Ministry of the Environment, so it is much more difficult to achieve anything at the Ministry of Industry and Trade than at the Ministry of the Environment.” (R1)
	“We have big players in agriculture who have made it to the highest echelons of politics. The fact is that subsidies are given to companies that already make profits from their business activities, and in my opinion, public funds, which are what these subsidies are supposed to be, should not be used to boost their own business, but rather to maintain the landscape and biodiversity and to ensure food security, but also food security of a certain quality.” (R4)

Table 4: List of enablers and disablers on the narrative level with supporting quotes from the interviews

Enabler	Supporting quote
Redefinition of organic farming	“Whatever field you can imagine, people are recruited from these fields who find meaning in getting engaged in rural areas, getting engaged in nature, often framing it in terms of climate change, wanting to contribute in some way to maintaining the ecosystem through farming. They see a whole range of values in this, from the big, systemic, climate-social ones to some personal fulfilment, where they were simply not satisfied with their work in the long term, as translators, lawyers, etc., and want to do something with their hands, be in contact with nature, with people, and so on. So I consider this to be a really huge change or a major contribution to potential change.” (R2)
	“(…) and that includes an increase in the number of organic farmers, an increase in the number of Czech organic foods, etc., etc. And I feel that a huge change is currently taking place in the sense that, as I would call it, a second generation of organic farmers is emerging after 35 years or so, and I consider this to be an extremely significant event, because for a long time, universities or rather educational programs at colleges and universities offering programs in organic farming, have been unable to systematically produce, in quote unquote, educated, experienced organic farmers who were willing to go into practice and devote themselves to this activity.” (R2)
Emphasis on a healthy lifestyle	“So this aspect, the fact that these topics were already becoming discursive, definitely helped a lot. There was a turning point, in my opinion, sometime in 2009/2010, when people started talking a lot about food quality and the relationship between purchasing behavior and its impact on nature and the landscape, and men in straw hats and with pitchforks started appearing in supermarkets. For me, this is a sign that it is now socially accepted. Once supermarkets start marketing this, it is clear that people actually understand and perceive it. The fact that it's greenwashing is, of course, another matter, but it

	has become accepted that agriculture is a really important aspect of society and that it needs to be approached in some way.” (R5)
An increased number of people searching for a connection with nature	“Or rather, it happened in parallel, and it is possible that the [Covid-19] pandemic contributed to this to some extent, in that many people, especially students and young people who would normally be attending classes, found themselves in a kind of vacuum where they had more time to think, to reflect more on themselves, their lives, their actions, and their direction. I think that during the [Covid-19] pandemic, more people connected with nature in the most general sense of the word. An interesting fact was that during the first wave of the pandemic, there were no animals available on the market because they had been completely sold out (...) Basically, anyone who could buy an animal did so (...), anyone who could started going out into nature, started growing more [produce], and so on.” (R2)
New peasantry movement	“(…) a new type of social class is emerging, or rather a new type of actors, often people from rural areas or even cities, who are starting to farm in a completely new way. They farm on the outskirts of agglomerations, on the outskirts of cities, or directly within cities, which is largely due to the fact that municipalities and cities own land and agricultural land. (...) And I would also like to use the term “new peasants” for these actors. They all have higher education, they all have a very strong foundation, they have a lot of social capital. (...)” (R2)
Global crises	“Of those external influences, it is definitely the war in Ukraine, the energy crisis, and, of course, the impact on the Czech Republic, i.e., energy-saving tariffs (...); because at that time there was a kind of realization on the part of (...) especially the local governments, that being dependent only on fossil fuels is risky, which until then (...) didn't seem that way, but this external influence helped.” (R1)
	“I think it helped a lot that society got a break,(...) it allowed people to break free from their daily routine, whether work or study, and perhaps that was the first time for many people. I am sure that it allowed many people to think about what they really wanted to do, what they wanted to pursue.” (R2)
Discourse evolution due to generational shift	“So, I perceive that there are new trends here and that people want their own authentic content again, that it is no longer enough for them to simply declare that they are organic farmers, but that they want to belong to a broader group of people who have a specific set of values. At the same time, they want some freedom in the sense that they don't necessarily want certification because of the bureaucracy involved, because they perhaps don't feel that society demands organic food.” (R2)
	“(…) especially in agriculture (...), there is still a lot of pain and a big unhealed wound that communism left behind, so anything community-based has this bad aftertaste. So trying to implement community-based methods of farming here in our country is, in my opinion, madness, and we have managed to introduce it, and of course, thanks to the fact that new generations of people are growing up who are not burdened by this, it helps, of course, and thanks to this, even the older folks, who have this pain buried deep inside them, generationally, transgenerationally, are now accepting this.“ (R5)

Disabler	Supporting quote
Invisible themes	<p>“At the same time, mayors in particular realized that they had not addressed energy issues at all, that there was very little awareness of how the energy sector actually works, and that the issue was basically dealt with in the following way: I have gas, that's it, I don't need to worry about anything else. I don't need to worry about data on consumption and production... which is simply a fundamental thing that we have to start from if we want to transform the energy sector here in a logical and rational way, so we have to have something to build on, and this know-how was completely lacking here.” (R1)</p> <p>“The topic of transformation of the food system does not resonate in the Czech Republic or in the Czech environment, neither among the general consumer public nor among informed consumers. I feel that informed consumers are primarily concerned with food quality. This is also true of organizations that deal with agriculture and food systems at a more advanced or alternative level.” (R2)</p>
Co-optation of transformative topics	<p>“In fact, the concept and its meaning are being flattened because other actors are suddenly entering the picture. A typical example is the topic of agroecology and food sovereignty (...). A concept that brought in the term and content of social movements and farmers [by the] organizations representing farmers. But there is a great effort on the part of the agri-lobby or agribusiness lobby and other actors to actually fill it with their own content, so that in the end, a hybrid emerges, which is precisely a model that allows everyone to have their cake and eat it too. But in the end, I can say that it is actually impotent in the sense that it does not fulfil its purpose, partly because the radical subtext or radical content disappears from it.” (R2)</p>
Czech society strongly prefers to see itself as apolitical	<p>“And in the end, when someone has a goal, they will eventually achieve it anyway, even though everyone here is discussing the problem of access to land, that they don't have access to initial investments, that [there is] (...) a whole range of systemic prohibitions, harassment, etc.</p> <p>But at the same time, no one here is in danger of losing their life because they have occupied a piece of land, which they farm on, and they are stepping on the toes of some corporation. (...)</p> <p>So, for me, what's missing here is the mobilizing aspect, precisely because what we know from countries in the Global South, and partly from countries in Western and Eastern Europe, is a type of systemic violence, which in our country takes a different form, a latent one, which actually causes everyone to be worse off, but not so badly that they would actually mobilize and form some kind of political agenda.” (R2)</p>
Seeking individual solutions as opposed to the collective ones	<p>“I still perceive it as being on some level of individual values and individual strategies for fulfilling individual values. It is possible that this is due to the discourse of post-communism, an experience specific to the Czech Republic or Czechoslovakia, where getting together and creating common platforms is still something repulsive. And at the same time, this prevents the creation of any fully-fledged and effective strategies. I say this based on my experience over the last 15 years or so, when we have been trying to do this for a long time, and it always ended up with everyone wanting to play, in quote</p>

	<p>unquote, on their own turf. They consider their agenda so valuable and interesting that they don't really want to share it with others. And I sense a great reluctance to discuss food issues in a broader socio-political context.” (R2)</p>
<p>Societal sensitivity to certain topics and terms</p>	<p>„(...) In the Czech Republic, we're not allowed to talk about it, but throughout the West, community-supported agriculture is one of the applications, let's say, of those agroecological approaches to the functioning of society, which are very much based on solidarity, mutuality, some of those communist ideas, right? The entire Via Campesina movement, which is the largest agricultural institution in the world, stands for this and promotes it. They don't want to have a branch here because we're a bunch of (...). No, because they don't have any partners here, (...) the fight would be too much of a fight, and they don't want that, which is completely legitimate.“ (R5)</p>